

Extending the Scalability and Parallelization of SimuCoast Code to hybrid CPU+GPU Supercomputers

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Abstract

The aim of the project was to extend the scalability and parallelization strategy of SimuCoast code to enable the use of hybrid CPU+GPU supercomputers. The code is focused on increasing the understanding of coastal processes utilizing high performance computing (HPC) for the numerical simulation of the three-dimensional turbulent flow, which is induced in the coastal zone, and mainly in the surf zone, by wave propagation (oblique to the shore), refraction, breaking and dissipation. A model based on MPI+OpenACC has been implemented in order to increase the computing capabilities of the code. The adapted code was validated using data from the Vittori-Blondeaux simulation and it was tested using up to 512 computing nodes of the Piz Daint supercomputer.

1. Introduction

Coastal zones are areas of great importance for economic and environmental activities. Surface waves in the coastal zone induce oscillatory flow motions in the vicinity of the seabed. These wave-induced coastal flows interact with the sandy seabed and modify the bed shape by generating coherent small-scale bed structures, which are generally known as ripples (see Figure 1). The presence of ripples in oscillatory flows is important due to the impact they have on the seabed roughness. The bed roughness directly affects the near-bed boundary layer hydrodynamics, which in turn controls sediment transport in coastal areas. Consequently, accurate prediction of sediment transport rates is an important element in morphological studies in coastal marine environments.

The simulation of coastal phenomena involves the numerical solution of highly coupled differential equations. The discrete equations are represented with a mesh, which for the sake of accuracy must have millions of cells to capture all the physical phenomena. Furthermore, the turbulent nature of the simulated flows requires the solution of several wave periods, such that the resulting time averages are meaningful. This makes the collecting of results a lengthy process that takes thousands of computing hours. The only way of executing such complex simulations in a reasonable time is by using supercomputing facilities.

The constant evolution of the supercomputers makes the development of parallel algorithms a rather difficult task. During the last few years, this evolution has been driven by the power consumption constraints of the systems [1]. Consequently, the level of intra-node parallelism has been increased by the introduction of multicore-CPU or accelerators (GPUs, Intel MIC, FPGA, etc). These new trends demand scalable algorithms with a higher degree of parallelism, as well as compatibility with fundamentally different parallel architectures. The present work is oriented to enabling our coastal flow simulation code (SimuCoast) to exploit hybrid CPU+GPU supercomputers. The implementation strategy consists in using a two level parallelisation. First, the inter node computations are tackled by using MPI communications and a geometric domain decomposition. On the other hand, the intra node execution is implemented using a directive based approach by means of OpenACC. By doing so, the portability between different architectures (CPU or GPU) is simplified to just switching some compilation flags.

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The paper is organized as follows. First, the math model used for the simulations of coastal flows is described. Second, the implementation strategy utilized in the simulations is presented. Then, numerical results validate the code and test its scalability. Finally, conclusions and directions for future work are briefly discussed.

Figure 1 Typical rippled sea bottom

2. Modelling approach

In the large eddy simulation (LES) approach, all flow structures are separated into the large, energy-containing eddies, which are directly resolved by the computational grid and the sub-grid contributions, which are parameterized. Using the characteristic scales of a_0 , U_0 and $0.5\rho U_0^2$, (where ρ is the fluid density), the resulting non-dimensional equations of motion for an incompressible flow become,

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(u_i u_j) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + \frac{1}{Re} \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} + f_i$$

where u_i are the resolved velocity components, t is the time, x_i are the three Cartesian coordinates denoted hereafter as the streamwise, x , spanwise, y , and vertical, z , directions of the numerical domain. Variable p is the dynamic pressure, τ_{ij} are the subgrid scale stresses (SGS), Re is the Reynolds number and f_i represents a source term associated with the implementation of the Immersed Boundary IB method for the enforcement of non-slip boundary conditions on the immersed bed surface. The dynamic pressure is split according to the expression:

$$p = P + \delta P$$

where P is the imposed dynamic pressure of the external flow, and δP is the dynamic pressure correction to the presence of the solid boundary.

To parameterize the SGS stresses, the simplest eddy-viscosity Smagorinsky (1963) model [2] is used:

$$\tau_{ij} = -2\nu_t \overline{S_{ij}} = -2(C_s \bar{\Delta})^2 |\overline{S}| \overline{S_{ij}}$$

where ν_t is the eddy-viscosity and $\overline{S_{ij}}$ is the resolved strain rate tensor, $C_s = 0.1$ is a model parameter, $\bar{\Delta} = (\Delta x \Delta y \Delta z)^{1/3}$ is the filter width.

For the introduction of the rippled bed in the computational domain, which is discretized with a structured Cartesian grid, the IB method is utilized [3]. The main advantage of this approach is that the efficient, energy conserving Cartesian solvers, which have been routinely used in direct numerical simulation (DNS) and LES over the past years, can be applied to complex geometrical configurations in a straightforward manner [4].

The governing differential equations are spatially discretized using second order, central finite-differences on a Cartesian staggered grid. The Navier-Stokes equations are discretized through a two-stage, time-splitting (fully explicit Adams-Bashforth) scheme, where an intermediate velocity is computed explicitly, taking into account only the external dynamic pressure of the form:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \cos(\omega t) + \beta \cos(2\omega t)$$

Where ω is the radial wave frequency defined in terms of the wave period (T) as $\omega = 2\pi/T$. The external dynamic pressure is temporally discretized using a second order trapezoidal rule.

3. Implementation strategy

SimuCoast has been developed as an object oriented in-house code focused on the simulation of coastal flows by means of DNS and LES models. A multilevel parallelization that combines different kinds of parallelism is required due to the variety of competing architectures and frameworks in current supercomputers.

The connectivity between nodes is obtained by means of a distributed memory approach with communications executed using MPI. The strategy consists in performing a domain decomposition algorithm in which the grid is divided in N non-overlapping subdomains. Additional halo cells are added to each subdomain to keep the consistency of the discretization. Each subdomain is associated with an MPI process, and communication episodes are executed each time the unknowns located in the interface cells need to be calculated.

At the node level a shared memory MIMD parallelism is needed for the multicore CPUs, or a Single Instruction Multiple Threads (SIMT) for accelerators like GPUs. Here, our strategy consists in using an OpenACC implementation that allows us to switch between platforms by just changing some compilation flags. Thus, the algorithm consists of a two-level hybrid MPI + OpenACC parallelization (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Levels of parallelism and programming models exploited by SimuCoast in a hybrid supercomputer.

For the intra node implementation we need to consider that the SimuCoast code can be divided into two main phases: I) the explicit part that loops over a mesh in order to calculate discretized operators; and II) the Poisson equation (implicit) that must be solved once per time-integration step. The most common iterative solver utilized is the Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient (PCG) which consists of algebraic operations that are compatible with the stream processing model required to run on the GPU. In addition, a direct solver based on the FFT can be used when there are periodic boundary conditions. In this case, data transformations and communications are required in order to avoid the complexity of applying the FFT in parallel. Then, the solver can be divided into 4 steps: I) Redistribute the initial partition into slices II) Redistribute slices into columns III) applying back and forward Fourier transformation and IV) Solve the 1D systems resulting from the Fourier diagonalization.

The discretized operators and the solvers are compatible with the directive based implementation, because they are based on structured loops that sweep the local domain for updating the unknowns. The iterations within those loops are independent of each other, therefore facilitating the use of tools like OpenACC.

4. Results

The new implementation strategy of the code was developed on the Cartesius supercomputer in SURFsara and the scalability tests were performed on the Piz Daint supercomputer from CSCS; these are respectively Tier-1 and Tier-0 systems of the Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE). The numerical experiments have been carried out in two stages: first the validation of the parallel implementation, and second, the analysis of the parallel performance of the code.

Validation

First, the computational model was set up to repeat the numerical simulation of oscillatory flow over two-dimensional ripples by Blondeaux and Vittori (1991) [5] and Scandura et al. (2000) [6] in which the instantaneous spanwise vorticity field during the first wave cycle was presented and discussed. The relative dimensions of the ripple were $L_r = 1.33\alpha_0$, $h_r/\alpha_0 = 0.2$, where L_r is the ripple length and h_r its height. The coordinates of the rippled bottom are described by the equations proposed by Sleath [7]. The size of the domain equals one ripple length on both x and y directions and two ripple lengths on the z direction. The grid is uniform with $N_x N_y N_z = 512 \times 128 \times 256$. In the present test case, the DNS of the laminar flow over the rigid rippled bed was performed at $Re = 1250$ and the flow starts with $u_i = 0$. As it can be seen in Figure 3, the results are in excellent agreement with the previous numerical simulations.

Figure 3 Spanwise vorticity, ω_y , at $t = \pi/2$, $t = \pi$, $t = 3\pi/2$, $t = 2\pi$, ($L_r = 1.33\alpha_0$, $h_r/\alpha_0 = 0.2$, $Re = 1250$). Left column - Blondeaux & Vittori (thin lines denote clockwise vorticity, while thick lines anticlockwise). Right column - Present results, (solid lines denote clockwise vorticity, while dashed lines anticlockwise)

The development of the vorticity during the first wave period, T , can be summarized as follows. At $T/4$, clockwise vorticity is generated along the bed profile and particularly near the crest of the ripple. In the second half of the cycle ($2T/4$), when the flow reverses, the already generated vortex structures are no longer strengthened but are simply convected away by the local velocity. In addition, the free shear layer strengthens the anticlockwise vortices at the crests. At $3T/4$, the new anticlockwise vortices are ejected and they are affected by the presence of the convected clockwise vortex structures. Finally, at T , the flow reverses and new clockwise vortices start to be created at the trough, while the already generated vortices are advected.

Intra-node

The development of the OpenACC version of the code was carried out on the Cartesius system. The results obtained for the parallelization based on OpenACC were compared with an MPI-only version of the code, and with an MPI+OpenMP version of the code. The MPI-only version was taken as a reference and the relative speedup of the different implementations is presented in Figure 4 for different grid sizes. Note that the MPI+OpenACC (CPU) version has nearly the same performance as the MPI+OpenMP version, proving that its use is reasonable for engaging the CPU. On the other hand, the MPI+OpenACC (GPU) outperforms up to 2.6 times the MPI-only version for the convection diffusive operator. Such speedup is increased up to 4 times if we consider also the rest of the discretized operators.

Figure 4 Performance of different implementations for the discretized operators in intra node execution.

Inter-node

The next step was to test the scalability of the new implementation on the Tier-0 PRACE facility at CSCS (Piz Daint). Figure 5 shows the strong speedup for the discretized operators of SimuCoast engaging up to 512 nodes using meshes of 500 and 1000 million cells. The parallel efficiency is about 68% when using 512 nodes. The speedup degradation is explained by two factors: i) the increase of processes involved in the point-to-point MPI communications required to update the unknowns at each time step; ii) the fall in occupancy of the GPU due to the smaller sub-domains. As a result, the ratio between communications and computations increases on the side of communications, so the communications overhead increases as reported in a previous experience with a similar CFD implementation [8].

Figure 5 Strong speedup of the discretized operators using MPI+OpenACC (GPU)

Figure 6 shows the strong speedup for the iterative PCG and the direct 2FFT solver using the largest mesh. The iterative solver has a parallel efficiency (PE) of 57% for the 512 nodes execution. This represents a drop in performance (-11 points) with respect to the discretized operators subroutines. The slowdown is consequence of the MPI_Allreduce operations within the iterative solver and that do not exist in the discretized operators. Such a drop in performance is even more significant in the direct 2FFT solver with a parallel efficiency of 39% (-29 points). In this case, the data transpositions produce performance degradation due to the all-to-all communications that are performed within MPI subgroups as has been observed when working with problems with one periodic boundary condition [9]. Nonetheless, despite the lower PE, the 2FFT runs are still 67X times faster in average than the iterative PCG.

Figure 6 Strong speedup of the Poisson solvers.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

In this PRACE Preparatory Access Type D project we have extended the parallelization of SimuCoast enabling the use of hybrid CPU+GPU supercomputers. The new GPU implementation allows us to run up to 4.7 times faster than our previous code for the discretized operators of the algorithm. In addition we have developed a new direct solver applicable to our coastal flows with two periodic boundary conditions. Such a solver is capable of running up to 67 times faster than the iterative Preconditioner Conjugate Gradient. Finally, the scalability of SimuCoast was successfully tested engaging up to 512 nodes of Piz Daint supercomputer. From a scientific point of view, this is an important step in order to move forward in the simulation of more complex physical phenomena at higher Reynolds numbers in a reasonable time.

Future work will integrate additional physical models and algorithms that currently exist in the MPI-only version of SimuCoast code. The plan would be to develop a code that simulates two-phase flows coupled with sediment transport and morpho-dynamics. Such simulations require a smaller time integration step in order to capture all the physical phenomena under consideration. Therefore, larger scale simulations are needed. In terms of HPC, one

of the developments that we would like to explore is the co-execution model that allows using all the computing resources on heterogeneous clusters. Such co-execution is associated with the development of load balancing techniques that distribute efficiently the workload between the CPUs and GPUs.

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